

1 **BAIAP2L1 expression is associated with treatment resistance in humans with Rheumatoid Arthritis**
2 **treated with the TNF-alpha blocker infliximab.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Treatment resistance in autoimmune and inflammatory diseases including Rheumatoid Arthritis, Multiple
8 Sclerosis, and Crohn's Disease are poorly understood. Glucocorticoid resistance and cytokine-associated
9 pathways associated modulation of cell death are two major mechanisms by which treatment resistance in
10 autoimmune and inflammatory disease can be approached for clinical intervention that aims to provide
11 sustained control of disease. We studied treatment resistance in humans treated with the TNF α
12 monoclonal antibody infliximab by measuring total transcription with next generation technologies in the
13 blood of Rheumatoid Arthritis patients based on treatment response. We identified BAIAP2L1 as a
14 component of the infliximab resistance signature in RA. Consistent with a role for BAIAP2L1 in
15 inflammatory disease, BAIAP2L1 was expressed at high levels in the blood of humans with Crohn's
16 Disease. In human hematopoiesis, BAIAP2L1 was expressed in a developmental stage-specific manner,
17 down-regulated during differentiation of the HSC to lymphoid and myeloid lineages in NK cells,
18 granulocytes and CD4⁺ T-cells, demonstrating subversion of HSC-specific BAIAP2L1 during propagation
19 of inflammatory disease. Compensatory changes in expression of IAP/BIRC family genes in the immune
20 system in response to treatment with TNF inhibitors involving contributions from the epigenetic
21 background are likely of relevance to treatment resistance in autoimmune and chronic inflammatory
22 diseases.

23 **References**

24 1. Vince, J.E., Wong, W.W.L., Khan, N., Feltham, R., Chau, D., Ahmed, A.U., Benetatos, C.A.,
25 Chunduru, S.K., Condon, S.M., McKinlay, M. and Brink, R., 2007. IAP antagonists target cIAP1 to induce
26 TNF α -dependent apoptosis. *Cell*, 131(4), pp.682-693.
27
28